

FEEDBACK FROM PARTICIPANTS' ETHICS

ADVISORY BOARDS

Deliverable Code: D7.3

Prepared by: Chiara Pandolfini (IRFMN)

Revised by: Giulia Irene Ghilardi (IRFMN), Guido Bertolini (IRFMN)

Version: Final

Date: 30/05/2025

Dissemination level: PUBLIC

Project: eCREAM

enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

Grant Agreement no. 101057726

**Funded by
the European Union**

Summary

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction.....	3
Context in project	3
Objective of deliverable.....	4
2. Pre-submission process	4
3. Table of current status of protocol submissions and ethics committee replies	6
4. Comments on ethics committee replies.....	7
5. Conclusions.....	7

Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the current status of the ethics committee submissions and replies for the three different eCREAM studies in the participating countries of the eCREAM project. The three studies are called 1) Development and validation of a natural language processing tool to enable clinical research in emergency and acute care medicine: retrospective cohort study (NLP-DeVal); 2) Propensity to hospitalize patients from the ED in European centers - An observational retrospective quality-of-care study (Use Case 1); and 3) Development of a multipurpose dashboard to monitor the situation of emergency departments - An observational retrospective study (Use Case 2).

This deliverable was originally foreseen for August 2023, but was delayed due to various reasons described in the project's first Periodic Report (e.g., legal and organisational complexities, addition of a third study deemed necessary for the project and prioritised with respect to the other two). Furthermore, the necessary documentation for submission of study protocols required by ethics committees within single countries and between different countries varies. Additional requests for further documentation on the part of single ethics committees must also be taken into consideration, as does the frequency of the committees' decisional meetings. These aspects lead to a fragmented situation in terms of permission to proceed in some centres and the need to wait in others.

This deliverable provides a description of the initial process that was undertaken to make the protocols suitable for submission and, for each of the three studies, provides a table reporting the current status of the ethics committee submissions and approvals in the participating centres of the eCREAM project.

1. Introduction

Context in project

The eCREAM project has three main aims:

- 1) to develop new technical solutions to extract reliable clinical information from structured and unstructured data contained in different electronic patient files;
- 2) to FAIRify (i.e., make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) the databases created for clinicians, researchers, health policymakers and citizens, while respecting the European and national legislation;

3) to pilot the exploitation of the established databases in two relevant use cases: i) assessment of ED propensity to hospitalise a patient, and ii) development of a dashboard to be used by citizens and policymakers to improve the quality of care in ED.

More specifically, for the third aim, two use cases, Use Case 1 and Use Case 2, were designed to test the eCREAM project's solutions for accurate, automatic, data extraction from the electronic health records (EHRs) of the participating emergency departments in the project's countries.

Additionally, as explained in the eCREAM project's first Periodic Report, an additional study was introduced once the project began, the NLP-DeVal study. The aim of this study is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art language model for the six languages of the project (English, Greek, Italian, Polish, Slovakian, and Slovenian) that is able to interpret the free text EHR contents and extract crucial information from them, to be used for the UC1 and UC2 studies to make accurate analyses and predictions.

Objective of deliverable

This deliverable describes the lengthy process that was undertaken to adhere to the Italian and European privacy regulations before the protocols' submissions, provides a table summarising the current status of the protocols' submissions to the ethics committees, and summarises the different types of replies received from the ethics committees.

2. Pre-submission process

Significant efforts were made before submission of the three protocols to the coordinating ethics committee in Italy. These efforts involved discussions on the part of the coordinating partner, the IRFMN, with legal experts to decide on the best strategy for submission of the protocols. The discussions involved deciding whether it would be better to submit a single protocol covering all three studies or three individual protocols, and the legal bases for data protection to apply in each case.

Given that collecting consent from patients would be impossible due to the large number of patients that visit EDs and the chronic staff shortages, the IRFMN approached several experts on legal issues related to clinical research at the national and international levels, as well as the ECRIN partner, to analyze the problems and possible solutions.

Following these discussions, the study design for Use Case 1 was changed from a prospective to a retrospective one to minimize issues related to identifying an alternative legal basis for participants' consent. For the Use Case 2 study it was decided that data would be aggregated, and therefore anonymized, to minimize the risk of patient identification in case of a data breach.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) stipulates that each member state has the power to add additional protection rules, and this was the case in some of the states involved in the eCREAM project, first and foremost Italy. The IRFMN had to write a letter to the Italian National Data Protection Authority describing the privacy issues and asking for approval to proceed without patient consent (as described above, for Use Case 1), as this step was obligatory at the time for Italy. The Italian legislation changed in May 2024, however, and made this step unnecessary.

Submissions to the participating centres then began, and were met with many hurdles from the centres' data protection offices due to requests for additional information, including on technical aspects, given the complexity of the studies. These additional hurdles contributed to the delays in submissions.

3. Table of current status of protocol submissions and ethics committee replies

Country*	Centre	City	NLP-DEVAL PROTOCOL		UC1 PROTOCOL		UC2 PROTOCOL	
			Date submitted	Approval	Date submitted	Approval	Date submitted	Approval
Italy	Ospedale San Giovanni Bosco **	Turin	07/2024	07/2024	12/2024	12/2024	12/2024	01/2025
Italy	Aou Policlinico 'G.Rodolico – San Marco'	Catania	07/2024		No need for approval (01/2025)			
Italy	Asst Grande Ospedale Metropolitano Niguarda	Milan	09/2024	10/2024	No need for approval (03/2025)			
Italy	Ospedale San Luigi Gonzaga	Orbassano (TO)	10/2024	10/2024	09/2024	04/2025	09/2024	04/2025
Italy	Ospedale Sant'andrea	Vercelli	Submission not necessary (1/2025)					
Italy	Asst Papa Giovanni XXIII	Bergamo	11/2024	12/2024	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale Maggiore Carlo Alberto Pizzardi	Bologna	11/2024	11/2024	04/2025	Waiting	04/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale di Chivasso	Chivasso (TO)	04/2025	04/2024	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale Maggiore	Lodi	04/2025	04/2025	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Italy	Fondaz. IRCCS Ca' Granda Osp. Maggiore Policlinico	Milan	01/2024	01/2025	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale Luigi Sacco	Milan	04/2025	04/2025	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale Santa Maria Delle Grazie	Pozzuoli (NA)	09/2024	09/2024	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale degli Infermi	Rivoli (TO)	11/2024	11/2024	No need for approval (03/2025)			
Italy	Aou Ss Antonio e Biagio E C. Arrigo	Alessandria	07/2024	Waiting	04/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale Santa Maria Annunziata	Bagno a Ripoli (FI)	01/2025	Waiting	01/2025	Waiting	01/2025	Waiting
Italy	Ospedale San Martino	Genova	01/2025	Waiting	-		-	
Italy	Ospedale Sant'Eugenio	Rome	-		-		-	
Poland	Uniwersytet Jagiellonski	Kraków	04/2025	04/2025	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Poland	Hospital Emergency Ward, Military Hospital	Kraków	04/2025	04/2025	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Poland	Stefan Zeromsky Specialist Hospital	Kraków	04/2025	04/2025	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Poland	University Hospital Krakow	Kraków	04/2025	04/2025	05/2025	Waiting	05/2025	Waiting
Slovenia	Univerzitetni Klinicni Center Maribor	Maribor	03/2025	Waiting	04/2025	Waiting	04/2025	Waiting
UK	Ashford and St Peter's Hospitals NHS Found. Trust	Surrey	05/2025 Single national submission - Waiting					
UK	Royal Surrey County Hospital	Guildford						
UK	Frimley Park Hospital	Camberley						
Greece	University General Hospital of Heraklion	Heraklion	-		***			
Greece	General Hospital of Chania, St George	Chania	-					
Greece	General Hospital "Venizelio-Pananaio"	Heraklion	-					
Greece	General Hospital of Agios Nikolaos	Lasithi	-					
Greece	General Hospital of Rethymnon	Rethymnon	-					

* List is in order of country and approval status

** Coordinating ethics committee

*** It should be noted that Greece will not be participating in the UC1 and UC2 studies because Crete does not currently use an electronic health record for the emergency department.

4. Comments on ethics committee replies

The approval status of the different protocols by the ethics committees between, and within, countries, varies. After the initial delays in submission due to the legal and organisational complexities, the partners began to submit the different protocols.

Differences between the ethics committees' required documentation, differing legal complexities, and adaptation of the protocols to the different countries, as expected, also needed to be factored in to the submissions.

Additionally, differences between ethics committees in their approach to the studies and to study approvals in general, contributed to the fragmented situation. The replies varied from no need for approval of any of the three studies once the protocols were viewed, to no need for approval once the coordinating ethics committee in Turin, Italy, gave its approval, to the need for approval of each individual study. In the UK, a single submission for all three studies was feasible, and approval, when given, will cover all participating centres.

5. Conclusions

After the initial delays in submission, the partners began to submit the three study protocols. Differences in the approaches to the studies and in the approval procedures from various ethics committees, as expected, also contributed to delays and to the fragmented submission status. The eCREAM partners are, however, currently catching up with the submissions and approvals are well underway.